

Triterpenes from *Derris scandens* (Roxb) Benth

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On account of its therapeutic value¹ the root of *Derris scandens* (Roxb) Benth was subjected to chemical investigation by several groups²⁻⁵, who reported the isolation of several oxygen heterocycles. The present note describes the isolation of a low melting solid, lupeol, taraxerol and β -sitosterol from the aerial part of the plant.

The petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract (8 hrs) of the dried and powdered stem and leaf of the plant (1.27 kg.) was separated into ether soluble (20.1 g) and ether insoluble (3.63 g) fractions. The ether insoluble fraction yielded only a neutral waxy solid (0.02 g) m.p. 68–70°, $(\alpha)_D + 0^\circ$ (CHCl_3), presumably a straight chain saturated compound. (Tetra nitromethane test—negative).

The ether soluble part was separated into neutral and acidic fractions. The latter fraction gave no crystallisable acidic matter, even after esterification and chromatography. The neutral fraction (5.58 g) was chromatographed over activated alumina (150 g). Elution with petroleum ether : benzene (7 : 3) furnished a solid (0.1 g), m.p. 165–185° which on re-chromatography followed by acetylation and crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and acetone yielded lupeol acetate, m.p. 208–210°, (Positive Libermann-Burchard test, positive T.N.M. test), $(\alpha)_D + 38.4^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen.

On further elution of the above column with petroleum ether : benzene (3 : 2) a solid, m.p. 258–268° was obtained (I.R. peak at 3580 cm^{-1}), which on acetylation followed by crystallisation from chloroform and acetone gave taraxerol acetate, m.p. 292–294°, $(\alpha)_D + 8.38^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical (mixed m.p., I.R.) with an authentic specimen. On hydrolysis, it furnished pure taraxerol, m.p. and mixed m.p., 265–269°, $(\alpha)_D + 0^\circ$ (CHCl_3).

Finally, the column on elution with ether : chloroform (1 : 4) furnished a solid (0.54 g), which on crystallisation from rectified spirit yielded β -sitosterol, m.p. 130–132°, identical (mixed m.p.) with an authentic specimen. On acetylation it gave β -sitosterol acetate, m.p. and mixed m.p. 124–125°, $(\alpha)_D - 40.0^\circ$ (CHCl_3). All the compounds gave correct, C, H-analysis.

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